

Loose parts for children with autism: Design opportunities and implications

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Abstract Loose parts are ambiguous and open-ended materials that provide endless possibilities in children's play. Loose parts foster creative and dramatic play which in turn stimulates the development of children's social, emotional and cognitive skills. In this paper we explore the potential value of loose parts for children with autism because their development of said skills tends to either not happen or at a very low pace. We describe the effects of a lagging Theory of Mind and Sensory Integration Disorder, which are both often associated with autistic spectrum disorders. This brings the diverse and complex nature of these disorders to light, virtually excluding universal design guidelines. However, several concrete design implications and opportunities are suggested. Our next steps entail engaging with autistic children in their context and trying out tailor made loose parts.

Keywords Autism, Design for play, Inclusive design, Child development, Sensory integration disorder

Introduction

Play is important for children's social, emotional, and cognitive development (Frost, Wortham, & Reifel, 2012). Of the many different types of play exhibited by children, 'dramatic play' is significantly beneficial due to its complex nature. By acting out long scenarios, whilst adopting many different roles, children develop a vast array of skills including language skills, speech skills, cooperative skills, problem solving skills and other advanced social skills (Sroka, 2006).

Dramatic play is particularly stimulated by so-called 'loose parts' (Daly & Beloglovsky, 2015; Nicholson, 1971). 'Loose parts' are movable objects and materials that are ambiguous to some extent, allowing children's creativity to determine its use or purpose. Examples of loose parts are pinecones, soup cans or car tires. They can also be purposely designed; for example large Styrofoam blocks (Maxwell, Mitchell, & Evans, 2008) or LEGO. A timeless example of a loose part that stimulates dramatic play is a simple large cardboard box.

The effects of loose parts on children and their play has been studied thoroughly, however most of the work is conducted on typically developing children (Sroka, 2006). Very little research has been done on how non-typically developing children play with loose parts. In this paper we focus on children with autism. The American Psychiatric Association states that the "essential features of Autistic Disorder are the presence of markedly abnormal or impaired development in social interaction and communication and a markedly restricted repertoire of activity and interests" (APA, 1994). The presence and severity of these features differ greatly between individuals. Aside from lacking communication and social skills, individuals with autism can also lack creativity (Sroka, 2006) and tend to show little to no

interest in activities that lie outside of their often sole preoccupation (for example, they can be fascinated with astrology, dinosaurs, trains or even batteries).

For children with autism the aforementioned skills tend to not develop or at a very low pace. Because these skills are implemented and honed during play their perception and implementation of play is inherently different, especially at younger ages. We see an opportunity for designing loose parts that stimulate the development of communication and social skills in children with autism.

This paper will first discuss the nature of autistic children in greater detail and the implications for designing loose parts for them. The paper will focus on two separate conditions that are often associated with autism and can account for most of the child's behavior: a lagging Theory of Mind and Sensory Integration Disorder.

Lagging of Theory of Mind

Theory of Mind (ToM) entails the grasp of the concept that every individual person has a mind of his or her own and that they perceive things in their own way. Having 'a developed ToM' means being able to 'put oneself in someone else's shoes', or being able to describe, understand and predict the emotions, intentions, motivations and perception of others (Korkmaz, 2011). Having an underdeveloped- or lagging of ToM can result in having a rather egocentric perspective on life.

The effects of a lagging Theory of Mind

Although normally developing children between the ages of 3-4 show signs of a developing ToM, a child with autism will either not show these signs or at a much later age (Korkmaz, 2011; Sroka, 2006). Figure 1 shows an example of the false-belief test, which

Figure 1. An example of a false belief test. The child answers incorrectly which, if the child is above the age of 4, indicates an underdeveloped Theory of Mind. The false answer comes from the fact that the child does not realize that 'Billy' will perceive the box of crayons in his own way and does not share the knowledge that the child himself has.

demonstrates the principle and is often used to evaluate a subject's ToM.

For children with autism a lagging ToM can hinder play in two main ways aside from the inevitable and obvious difficulty with social integration. These children have difficulty using 'actors' (like dolls) to facilitate dramatic play and engaging in 'make-believe'.

Being able to perceive the world through something other than one's own eyes is a prerequisite for (individual) dramatic play facilitated through props or toys. Pretending a doll represents a person during play, especially when imagining a conversation between two dolls, requires the child to perceive the world through the eyes of the actors (dolls). Because this process requires a developed ToM these children are less likely to use props like dolls as actors (Sroka, 2006).

A child with autism and a lagging ToM can have difficulty with make-believe for two reasons. The first of which is the same as the aforementioned reason for difficulty with actor substitution; having to adopt a role. The second important factor is that a large part of make-believe is using (ambiguous) objects to represent something other than what they actually are; like pretending a wooden block is a car. This requires the acceptance of the fact that objects can have multiple interpretations – accepting that the subject's interpretation might not be the only one – which is part of the ToM skillset (Lillard, 1993). An underdeveloped ToM can directly impede this ability to pretend.

Design implications for a lagging ToM

The two abovementioned effects (difficulty with actor substitution and difficulty with make-believe) associated with a lagging or underdeveloped ToM should be taken into account when designing loose parts for autistic children. The implications discussed below are summarized in Table 1.

The decreased ability to use props or toys as actors can be translated into a design requirement by stating that the loose part should not solely be interpretable as a separate entity (a toy animal) but instead they should be passive entities (like tools). Depending on the individual's ability, extensions of the user's entity are also possible (the user in a toy car).

The difficulty with make-believe can be taken into account by regulating the degree of ambiguity and finding the right balance. Making the loose part too

Table 1. The findings and recommendations related to a Lagging Theory of Mind (ToM).

Theory of Mind (ToM) related findings	Recommendation
Children with a lagging ToM have difficulty using actors during play, like dolls. They don't naturally bring the actor to life or pretend to be the actor.	Toys should not solely be interpretable as an entity that is not the user but instead by passive entities or possibly less abstract extensions of the user's entity.
Children with a lagging ToM have difficulty with make-believe. They have trouble letting go of a meaning once it has been attributed to an object and avoid objects if they can't attribute any meaning.	The ambiguity in the toys should be regulated. Too little and the toy misses the main value of a loose part but too much and a child won't know what to do with the toy.

ambiguous may result in that it does not resemble anything, and the child will not know ‘how’ to play with it and avoid interaction (Sroka, 2006). On the other hand making the loose part too directed is very limiting, because once a ‘use’ or ‘meaning’ has been attributed to a specific toy, the child will have difficulty letting go and will not naturally explore other possibilities, essentially missing the value of a ‘loose part’.

Sensory Integration Disorder

Researchers speculate that individuals with autism might have differences in their sensory perception, which is further strengthened by the supposed neurological cause behind the disorder (Hebert, 2003). Difficulty with sensory perception is often described as Sensory Integration Disorder (SID) which, although it is an ‘independent disorder’, is often associated with autistic children. ‘Sensory integration’ is the process of obtaining, analyzing and reacting upon sensations from one’s environment and own body.

The observable consequences of having SID are that children can get extremely over- or underwhelmed when exposed to seemingly trivial stimuli. These children can show hypersensitivity, hyposensitivity or both for the auditory, visual, tactile, olfactory (smell), gustatory (taste), vestibular (balance) and or proprioceptive (sense of self) senses (Hebert, 2003).

The effects of SID

Difficulty with SID can exhibit itself in many different severities. Most often children have a specific and seemingly arbitrary preference for- or dislike of- a certain sensation. For example a child can seriously dislike a certain type of food simply because of the way it ‘squishes’ or be fascinated by newspapers because of how they ‘crackle’. Other cases can involve the child extremely overreacting (from an observer’s perspective) or simply not reacting at all to certain stimuli. For example, a child can ‘panic’ when someone touches them whilst others have an extremely high pain threshold (Hebert, 2003).

The difficulty with the vestibular sense (sense of balance) can present itself in two different ways. A child with an under-aroused vestibular system can partake in extreme and repetitive moments of the hands, head or entire body to satiate their vestibular cravings (hand flapping, head rocking or suddenly sprinting). Since the vestibular system also regulates hand-eye coordination, difficulties coordinating one’s body or hands (difficulty with writing or catching a

ball) can also present themselves. On the other hand, a child with vestibular hypersensitivity can simply dislike excessive movements (Hebert, 2003).

The proprioceptive sense regulates one’s awareness of the relative position of one’s own body and limbs (sense of self, also called the ‘internal eye’). Corresponding difficulties exhibit themselves as general clumsiness but can also influence self-help tasks (like dressing oneself) or even cause oral-motor difficulties (during eating or speaking) (Hebert, 2003).

Design implications for SID

Due to the diverse nature of the difficulties associated with SID, any design of a loose part for autistic children with said difficulties should be tailor made to a certain extent since that which is enjoyable for one individual can most likely not be translated to the next. An overview of further recommendations is presented in Table 2.

Besides avoiding the unintentional overstimulation of a certain sense to which the child is hypersensitive, these discrepancies in sensory perception also provide opportunities. Hypersensitivity does not always lead to overstimulation; if the stimuli are kept subtle they remain manageable. By integrating a wide array of sensations into a series of loose parts a child can ‘explore’ these sensational variations in a controlled environment. For example, objects that offer different tactile qualities for the child to explore.

An under aroused vestibular system comes paired with a vestibular craving. An opportunity would be to allow a child to satiate this craving in a more meaningful, beneficial or less harmful manner than what they would normally resort to.

When dealing with children with a low proprioceptive sense their ‘clumsiness’ should be taken into account. These children have trouble estimating distances between themselves and others and when armed with large objects that they can pick up and swing around they can cause undesirable situations.

Conclusion

The complex and diverse nature of the disorders within the autistic spectrum makes it virtually impossible to create concrete and universal design implications for ‘ideal’ loose parts for autistic children. Associated conditions differ greatly in severity and nature, which implies that the loose parts should either be tailor-made or be adaptable to

Table 2. The findings and recommendations related to Sensory Integration Disorder.

Sensory Integration Disorder (SID) related findings	Recommendation
Children with SID can have an unpredictable but extreme like or dislike of certain sensations. They can be captivated but also repulsed by seemingly trivial experiences.	Taking a child’s preference into account, toys should be tailor made or adaptable and avoid overstimulation. Exploration of variations of their preference can be immensely captivating.
Children with SID can have (vestibular) hyposensitivity. This sensory numbness can come paired with a consequent craving to experience this sense.	Using a toy to facilitate this sensory satiation in a controlled manner can allow the experience to be more meaningful, less harmful or even beneficial.
Children with SID can have a low proprioceptive sense making them generally clumsy.	Avoid the use of large objects that can be picked up and swung around.

individual needs. However, we believe that loose parts can be designed for autistic children and can in turn provide them with the developmental benefits that come with the consequent dramatic play.

For example, individuals with an autistic disorder can exhibit hypersensitivity to certain senses, which could cause loose parts to be unexpectedly utterly intolerable. This means that any sensory discrepancies must be taken into account beforehand and designs must be tailor made to suit the individual child.

Aside from that, children with a lagging ToM (e.g. autistic children) have a lower tolerance of ambiguity and less intrinsic motivation to 'explore'. This means that loose parts must be self-explanatory to a certain degree or they might be ignored.

Next steps

'Play' is an important part of an autistic child's development and the potential for loose parts begs for future research. Our next step is doing a design study with children and caregivers building on the insights presented here and guidelines by van Rijn (2012). First, we will gain a better 'creative understanding' by personally engaging with several patients and caregivers. Based on this understanding we will design and evaluate tailor made loose parts. This step will consist of i) video observations and ii) sessions with parents and therapists in which the loose parts and video material serve to evoke discussion and reflection (see Stappers 2014). We hope to gain insights on i) the *degree of ambiguity* that is both tolerable and inspiring for autistic children and ii) the potential *role* of loose parts in children's play (in both self-initiated play and therapeutic play) and iii) how these loose parts can ultimately contribute to a child's social and cognitive development.

References

APA. (1994). *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders* (4th ed.). Washington: AMERICAN PSYCHIATRIC ASSOCIATION.

Daly, L., & Beloglovsky, M. (2015). *Loose Parts: Inspiring Play in Young Children*. St. Paul: Redleaf Press.

Frost, J. L., Wortham, S. C., & Reifel, S. (2012). *Play and Child Development*, Fourth Edition. Boston: Pearson.

Hebert, B. B. (2003, May). *DESIGN GUIDELINES OF A THERAPEUTIC GARDEN FOR AUTISTIC CHILDREN*. New Orleans: University of New Orleans.

Korkmaz, B. (2011). Theory of mind and neurodevelopmental disorders of childhood. *Pediatric research* 69, pp. 101R-108R.

Kuh, L. P., Ponte, I. C., Chau, C., & Valentine, D. (2014). Take It outside - Rethinking and Reclaiming Outdoor Play. In L. P. Kuh, *Thinking Critically about Environments for Young Children: Bridging Theory and Practice* (pp. 69-88). New York: Teacher Collage Press.

Lillard, A. S. (1993). Pretend play skills and the child's theory of mind. *Child development*, pp. 348-371.

Maxwell, L. E., Mitchell, M. R., & Evans, G. W. (2008). Effects of Play Equipment and Loose Parts on Preschool Children's Outdoor Play Behavior: An Observational Study and Design Intervention. *Children, Youth and Environments* 18(2), pp. 36-63.

Nicholson, S. (1971, October). How not to cheat children, the theory of loose parts. *Landscape Architecture* 62, pp. 30-34.

Sroka, N. E. (2006). *A META-ANALYSIS OF PUBLISHED LITERATURE ON THE ROLE OF LOOSE PARTS IN THE PLAY BEHAVIOR OF NON-TYPICALLY DEVELOPING CHILDREN*. Ithaca, New York: Cornell University.

Stappers, P. J. (2014). Prototypes as central vein for knowledge development. In L. Valentine (Ed.), *Prototype: Design and craft in the 21st century*. London: Bloomsbury.

van Rijn, H. (2012). *Meaningful Encounters: Explorative studies about designers learning from children with autism*. Delft: Delft University of Technology.